

The combined impact of thermal renovations and user behaviour on predicting residential heating energy use

Markus Dörn¹, Naomi Morishita¹, Azra Korjenic¹, and Thomas Bednar¹

¹*Institute for Building Construction and Technology, Research Centre for Building Physics and Building Acoustics, Vienna University of Technology, Vienna, Austria*

Keywords: user profile, energy-related occupant behaviour, energy certificate calculations, residential heating energy, single family homes

ABSTRACT

This paper compares the calculated heating energy demand to the actual energy use in three existing single family homes. Three case study houses built in 1957, 1965, and 1987, underwent phased thermal renovations and were studied using detailed data collected over several years. The two-storey detached homes with basements are situated in the Austrian Vorarlberger Highlands close to the western Austrian border.

The findings from a recent master's thesis completed at the Research Center of Building Physics and Sound Protection, Vienna University of Technology, compared the estimated to actual residential heating energy use in three existing single family homes. The results discussed below showed that the calculated values exceeded actual energy consumption by up to 35%. The main reasons for the discrepancies between the estimated values in the Austrian energy certificate calculations and the actual consumption showed that detailed input data including information about user behaviour, building services, climate data, and building construction are needed for accurate estimations (Dörn, 2011). The connection between phased thermal renovations and inhabitants' behaviour on energy consumption in relation to the energy estimates in the energy certificate calculations for individual single family homes are shown.

1. Introduction

Research by Müller et al. (2010) and Knoter (2010) have found that by improving the thermal envelope and building HVAC systems, a building's overall energy consumption can be decreased dramatically. In the study by Müller et al. (2010), thermal renovations of existing homes were predicted to become increasingly important in Austria increasing the relevance of detailed studies of the relationship of the quality of the thermal envelope, building services, and occupant behaviour to better understand the influence on total energy use in buildings. Unlike other building forms such as apartment houses, occupants have an impact on energy use in detached single family homes partially due to the fact that homeowners are able to make decisions about the type of heating and hot water systems in their homes, and due to dedicated versus shared energy bills (Kyrö et al., 2011). The findings of a study by Guerra Santin et al. (2009) where the combination of building characteristics, household type, and occupancy were investigated show that the effect of insulating the exterior envelope has a larger impact on energy use than occupant behaviour, even though behaviour impacts household energy use significantly. Guerra Santin et al. go on to show that in a breakdown of housing according to type that detached single family homes have the highest energy consumption, even with improvements of the exterior insulation levels signifying the importance of research into the energy use patterns in detached single family homes.

The findings from a recent master's thesis completed at the Research Center of Building Physics and Sound Protection, Vienna University of Technology, comparing the estimated to actual residential heating energy use in three renovated single family homes taking into account climate, the building

envelope, HVAC systems and user behaviour are discussed. The impact of phased thermal renovations and inhabitants' behaviour on energy consumption was compared to the energy estimates in the energy certificate calculations for three individual single family homes.

All figures, tables, and graphs originate from the master's thesis by Markus Dörn unless otherwise stated (Dörn, 2011).

2. Background on the existing houses

Each single family house has a basement, and is either two or three stories. The homes were thermally renovated in phases by changing and upgrading the HVAC systems and increasing thermal insulation levels to varying degrees in each house. Sections 2.2 to 2.4 will outline each building's main characteristics, building services, and user profiles.

Fig. 1. Views of Houses 1, 2, and 3

2.1 Climate data

Monthly climate data from 2001 to 2011 recorded at the Feldkirch weather station from the Austrian Central Institute for Meteorology and Geodynamics was used for the adjusted energy certificate calculations in the analyses shown in Section 3. The location of the weather station is within 18 km from all the houses and corresponds to the actual weather conditions for the measurement period. In comparison to the adjusted calculations, the standard energy certificate

calculations use regional climate data per climate region and altitude as outlined in ÖNORM 8110-5 (Austrian Standards Institute, 2010).

2.2 Building profiles

The planning permission drawings for each house were used for the base case scenarios. Information about the major building component constructions (roof, exterior walls, floor slabs) were given by the homeowners and compared to the building traditions of the periods. The construction material properties were taken from the online “Baubook” building element databank (Baubook, 2011). The homeowners also gave the dates of each renovation phase, allowing for energy consumption comparisons by date.

2.2.1 House 1 building characteristics

The two-storey house was built in 1987 and is shown in the leftmost image of Figure 1. The coloured building section below in Figure 2 shows the heated floors in yellow (ground and upper floor), the partially heated basement in green, and the unheated and unused attic in blue.

Fig. 2. House 1 section

Table 1 outlines the main existing building assemblies with their corresponding heat transfer coefficients and areas for both existing and renovated states.

Table 1. House 1 existing opaque building assemblies

	Area [m ²]	Existing	Renovated
		U-Value [W/m ² K]	
Ceiling to unheated attic	61	0.27	0.15
Ventilated façade	134	0.26	0.22
Slab on grade	93	0.94	0.94
Windows and doors	29	*	*

The mechanical equipment was replaced in 2005 and is discussed in greater detail in Section 2.3.1. In total, there are three thermal upgrade stages. The thermal envelope was renewed in two later stages: in January 2008, 10 cm of fibreglass insulation was added to the attic space; in

Proceedings of the 5th IBPC, Kyoto, Japan, May 28-31, 2012
September 2009, 5 cm of EPS was added to the basement ceiling and 3 cm of fibreglass to the exterior walls as part of the renewal of the ventilated exterior façade. The overall airtightness is estimated to have increased from $n_{50}=3.5 \text{ h}^{-1}$ to $n_{50}=3 \text{ h}^{-1}$ because of the façade renewal.

2.2.2 House 2 building characteristics

This two-storey house was built in 1965 and is shown in the middle image of Figure 1. Similar to House 1, the ground and first floors are heated and are shown in yellow in the building cross section in Figure 3. Both the basement and attic storeys are unheated and are shown in blue.

Fig. 3 House 2 section

Table 2 below summarizes the thermal properties of the existing and renovated building assemblies with their corresponding heat transfer coefficients and areas.

Table 2. House 2 existing opaque building assemblies

	Area [m ²]	Existing	Renovated
		U-Value [W/m ² K]	
Exterior wall	175	0.58	0.12
Ceiling to unheated attic	55	0.86	0.20
Floor to unheated, uninsulated basement	99	0.55	0.17
Floor slab over entrance	1.8	0.58	0.12
Windows and doors	29	2.62	0.89

The renovations occurred in three phases and the house was insulated in two parts. The attic was insulated with 22 cm fibreglass insulation in March 2008, and in September 2009, the exterior walls and the floor slab to the unheated basement were insulated with 20 cm EPS and 12 cm EPS respectively. The windows were also replaced in 2009 as summarized in Table 3 below.

Table 3. House 2 window areas and heat transfer coefficients

Cardinal direction	Area [m ²]	Existing	Renovated
		A x U [W/K]	A x U [W/K]
North	10	25	9.8
East	2.8	7.4	2.4
South	12	32	10
West	4.0	11	3.4
Totals	29	76	26

2.2.3 House 3 building characteristics

This two-storey house was built in 1987 and is shown in the rightmost image of Figure 4. In this case, only the ground floor is heated and shown in yellow in the building cross section in Figure 4. The basement, upper storey, and attic are unheated and are shown in blue.

Fig. 4. House 3 section

Table 4 outlines the main housing assemblies prior to and after renovation with corresponding heat transfer coefficients and areas.

Table 4. House 3 existing opaque building elements

	Area	Existing U-Value	Renovated U-Value
	[m ²]	[W/m ² K]	[W/m ² K]
Exterior wall	154	0.60	0.13
Ceiling to unheated, closed attic	81	0.25	0.13
Floor to unheated uninsulated basement	84	0.68	0.19
Basement wall above ground	31	1.20	0.15

The thermal renovations occurred in two steps. New windows were installed in 1998, increasing the overall airtightness of the house. In September 2010, the exterior façade was renewed. Additional EPS insulation was installed in the exterior walls (18 cm) and floor slab (12 cm) to the basement; 12 cm mineral wool insulated the unheated attic. The renewal also increased the airtightness of the exterior envelope to $n_{50}=2.5 \text{ h}^{-1}$.

2.3 HVAC equipment

Each house updated their HVAC (heating, ventilation and air conditioning) equipment as part of their thermal renovations. The following sections outline what equipment was in the house prior to the renewals, and what changes were implemented by the homeowners with corresponding dates.

2.3.1 House 1 HVAC equipment

The existing heating system is a water-based TRV (thermostatic radiator valve) radiator system using a gas boiler (built in 1978) to provide both DHW (domestic hot water) and room heating. The DHW tank and the gas boiler are located in the boiler room partially heated basement.

In 2005, the boiler was replaced, and underfloor heating was installed in both the kitchen and bathroom.

2.3.2 House 2 HVAC equipment

All HVAC equipment is found in the unheated basement boiler room. An “extra light” heating oil boiler, vintage 1978 provided room and DHW heating. There are TRV controlled radiators are in all ground and upper storey rooms. In March 2008, the mechanical equipment was replaced: a low temperature heating oil boiler (40°C supply temperature and 30°C return temperature) replaced the old boiler (60°C supply temperature and 50°C return temperature originally built prior to 1978); a larger DHW tank with 500 litre capacity replaced the 300 litre hot water tank to accommodate a new roof-mounted solar thermal system installation.

2.3.3 House 3 HVAC equipment

All building services are found in the unheated basement boiler room. Default values were used to estimate pipe lengths and pipe insulation. A low temperature boiler (40°C supply temperature and 30°C return temperature) was installed in 2001. Individual room heating is supplied by TRV’s and radiators. The kitchen, living room, and ground floor hallways are heated with a modern tiled stove. The excess heat produced by the tiled stove is used to heat the DHW supply. In September 2010, 10 m² of thermal solar panels were installed on the south-east side of the roof.

2.4 User behaviour

A questionnaire was distributed to the homeowners to establish the average period of time the homeowners were at home, the interior set point temperatures of individual rooms, and the ventilation patterns for each person. The homeowners were also interviewed to determine the amount of hot water used by bathing. Hot water use was categorized as per Table 5.

Table 5. Bathing patterns to determine hot water use.

Category	Hot water (litres/Person·day)
Water saving	25
Standard	30
Non water saving	50

The occupant behaviour data collected in the questionnaires and interviews was used to modify the user profile criteria in the adjusted calculations discussed in Section 3.

2.4.1 House 1 user profile

Two homeowners are present approximately 18 hours/day. The rooms are heated according to frequency of use with room use varying from high (daily) to low (approximately 3 weeks/year). The occupants are smokers, and mainly occupy the kitchen-living room which they ventilate hourly when occupied to rid the room of cigarette smoke. All other rooms are ventilated on demand. Table 6 shows the window ventilation rates, and the estimated infiltration rates for the house.

Table 6. House 1 window ventilation rates

Month	Single-sided window ventilation	Cross ventilation	Estimated infiltration	
			Existing	Renovated
January	0.07	0.01	0.35	0.30
February	0.07	0.01	0.35	0.30
March	0.08	0.01	0.35	0.30
April	0.09	0.02	0.35	0.30
May	0.09	0.02	0.35	0.30
June	0.10	0.03	0.35	0.30
July	0.09	0.03	0.35	0.30
August	0.10	0.03	0.35	0.30
September	0.09	0.03	0.35	0.30
October	0.09	0.01	0.35	0.30
November	0.08	0.01	0.35	0.30
December	0.07	0.01	0.35	0.30

The single-sided window ventilation rates are calculated using the following formula (European Committee for Standardization, 2004):

$$\dot{V}_{NV} = C_{ref} \cdot A \cdot \sqrt{H} \cdot \sqrt{\Delta T} \quad (1)$$

Where \dot{V}_{NV} is the single-sided air flow volume through the window opening (m³/h), C_{ref} is the exchange coefficient (m^{0.5}/h·K^{0.5}), A is the window opening area (m²), H is the height of the window opening (m), and ΔT is the temperature difference between outdoor and indoor air (K).

Window cross ventilation air flow volumes were calculated using the following formula:

$$\dot{V}_{CV} = \left(\frac{A_1}{2} + \frac{A_2}{2} \right) \cdot \sqrt{C_1 \cdot u^2 + C_2 \cdot H_{1,2} \cdot \Delta T + C_3} + \frac{\sqrt{C_4 \cdot u^2}}{\sqrt{A_1^{-2} + A_2^{-2}}} \quad (2)$$

Where, \dot{V}_{CV} is the cross flow air volume through the window opening (m³/h), C_n is the exchange coefficient, A_n is the area of the window opening per façade side (m), H is the window opening height (m), ΔT is the temperature difference between outdoor and indoor air (K), and u is the wind speed (m/s).

The infiltration rates have been estimated from the n₅₀ values according to (Aschoff and Grotjan, 2004).

2.4.2 House 2 user profile

Three people live in the house and are present for 16 hours/day on average. Ventilation patterns show high variance between houses. All windows are opened every morning for 10 to 15 minutes to freshen the air throughout the house. Window ventilation for shorter periods occurs on demand for all other occasions. Table 7 summarizes the natural ventilation rates for House 2, showing the actual single-sided and cross ventilation rates, and the calculated values for the house prior to and after the renovation.

Table 7. House 2 natural ventilation rates

Month	Single-Sided Window Ventilation	Cross Ventilation	Estimated Infiltration	
			Existing	Renovated
January	0.08	0.09	0.5	0.25
February	0.08	0.08	0.5	0.25
March	0.09	0.09	0.5	0.25
April	0.09	0.15	0.5	0.25
May	0.10	0.18	0.5	0.25
June	0.10	0.26	0.5	0.25
July	0.10	0.23	0.5	0.25
August	0.10	0.22	0.5	0.25
September	0.10	0.21	0.5	0.25
October	0.10	0.11	0.5	0.25
November	0.09	0.11	0.5	0.25
December	0.08	0.10	0.5	0.25

In relation to House 1, there are much higher cross-ventilation rates as the occupants ventilate the whole house each morning for 10-15 minutes.

2.4.3 House 3 user profile

Two people live in the house, and are at home for 18 hours/day on average. The upper floor has been unused for many years, and remains unheated during the winter. As the interior renovations were not completed by the beginning of the heating season for 2010, a post-renovation use profile was not observed. Table 8 summarizes the natural ventilation rates for House 3.

Table 8. House 3 natural ventilation rates

Month	Single Sided	Cross		Estimated Infiltration	
		Ground	Upper	Existing	Renovated
January	0.05	0.08	0.06	0.40	0.35
February	0.05	0.07	0.05	0.40	0.35
March	0.07	0.08	0.06	0.40	0.35
April	0.08	0.13	0.10	0.40	0.35
May	0.09	0.16	0.13	0.40	0.35
June	0.10	0.23	0.19	0.40	0.35
July	0.09	0.21	0.17	0.40	0.35
August	0.10	0.19	0.17	0.40	0.35
September	0.08	0.18	0.14	0.40	0.35
October	0.08	0.10	0.07	0.40	0.35
November	0.06	0.09	0.07	0.40	0.35
December	0.06	0.09	0.07	0.40	0.35

Although the upper storey is unheated in winter, the occupants ventilate the whole house each morning for about 12 minutes.

2.5 Energy consumption data

Energy consumption data for heating oil, gas, and electricity originated from a combination of energy bills, meter readings by the homeowners, and extrapolation of the available data. These values were used as the basis for the actual energy use for each home in the analysis section comparing calculated to actual energy use.

2.6 Energy certificate calculations

Energy certificates are required for every new construction and building renovation in Austria as part of the

implementation of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (Council of the European Union, 2002). The Austrian energy certificate calculations are based on the whole building and use the monthly balanced method to forecast the amount of end energy that will be used in the homes. Due to the holistic calculation approach, it is difficult to include more than one HVAC system, or different uses for different rooms (Österreichisches Institut für Bautechnik, 2007). Partial room heating is not considered, and the current user profile is a simple, static model assuming full occupancy for the whole year (Österreichisches Institut für Bautechnik, 2011).

2.7 User profile assumptions in the energy certificate calculations

The user profile used in the energy certificate calculations is outlined in ÖNORM B 8110-5 (Austrian Standards Institute, 2010). For single family homes, the calculation guidelines assume the following:

- fully occupied for the whole year (365 days/year and 24 hours/day);
- heated 24 hours/day during the heating season;
- heating set point temperature is 20°C
- window ventilation rate of 0.4 h⁻¹ ACH
- internal heat gains of 3.75 W/m² from people and electrical appliances during the heating season.

The energy certificate calculations in Section 3 use the standard profile as per the criteria listed above.

3. Analysis

The following section shows energy use for each house comparing actual energy values to calculated estimations based on the energy certificate calculations using the static user profile as outlined in Section 2.7.

Figure 5 shows an overview of the difference between actual and estimated heating energy use using actual energy consumption as a base case (100%) for each house shown in blue. Here it is seen that the energy uses for both Houses 1 & 2 have been similarly overestimated by approximately 35% despite adjustments with more accurate climate and user profile data. In Figures 5 to 9, actual energy use is shown in red, energy certificate calculations are in purple, and the adjusted energy certificate calculations with weather station climate data and updated user profiles from homeowner interviews and questionnaires are shown in blue.

Fig. 5. Comparison of estimated versus actual heating energy use in each case study house

Proceedings of the 5th IBPC, Kyoto, Japan, May 28-31, 2012
 In Figure 6, there is little change between the original and adjusted calculated values in comparison with the actual heating energy use. Actual use is lower than both sets of estimated values by a range of 20% and 37%. Heating energy bills for 2010 and 2011 were not available, and are thus excluded from the graph. In House 1, total annual heating energy use decreases by 7,800 kWh/a between 2002 and 2007, then increases the following year by 3,200 kWh/a.

Fig. 6. House 1 annual heating energy use from 2001 to 2010

Possible reasons for the upward swing in heating energy consumption can be related to a milder winter during the heating season for 2007, with colder exterior conditions returning in 2008, or lower occupancy.

Figure 7 shows actual and calculated annual heating energy uses for House 2 over four years from 2006 to 2010. Similar to House 1, both sets of calculations overestimate actual energy use, especially during the last recorded year after the exterior envelope was insulated. The graph also shows that despite efficiency improvements in heating equipment, the thermal renovations have a greater impact on overall heating energy use. Energy use prediction accuracy increases with thermal envelope improvements, and deviations for the adjusted calculated values from actual energy use decreases from 35% in 2008 to 12% in 2009. In House 2, annual heating energy use decreases overall by 21,922 kWh/a between 2006 and 2010.

Fig. 7. House 2 annual heating energy use from 2006 to 2010

Figure 8 shows energy flows in greater detail. The greatest amount of energy is spent for the annual fuel demand, heating energy demand, and transmission heat losses in the base case scenario. After all the renovations, annual energy flows are

significantly decreased in the same categories to show more evenly distributed energy flows throughout the house.

Fig. 8. House 2 breakdown of energy uses

Figure 9 below shows the comparative annual heating energy uses for House 3. Within the base case already exists a modern wood burning stove and a gas boiler installed in 2001. The next renovation phase took place in 2010, when the exterior envelope was insulated and a solar thermal array was installed. The heating energy bill for 2006/2007 was not available, and a portion of the heating energy use for the 2010/2011 heating season was available due to the completion of the study. Thus, a partial view of the impact of the thermal renovation is visible. Of the three case study houses, the heating energy use of House 3 is the most constant, fluctuating between 19,869 kWh/a and 22,761 kWh/a; a change of 2,892 kWh/a (13%). As only partial heating energy data is available for 2011, it was excluded from the annual energy use assessment.

Fig. 9. House 3 annual heating energy use from 2001 to 2011

Figure 10 shows a breakdown of energy uses for House 3. The actual energy use for the years 2006 (base case) and 2011 (renovated case) were taken for the analysis. Fuel demand (61%), heating energy demand (58%), and transmission heat losses (49%), exhibit the greatest changes from the base case scenario. The base case energy flows for House 3 is approximately half of House 2. In both scenarios, DHW use and internal gains remain constant, and show the least sensitivity to insulation and building equipment improvements.

The combination of heating systems increases the degree of uncertainty in energy use estimations as it becomes more difficult to make a standardized estimate the degree by which each heating system will heat a room. For example, the kitchen in House 3 has two heating systems, radiators with TRVs and a closed wood burning oven. The thermostats in the radiators will react by reducing the heat output as more heat is generated by the oven. Further research to assimilate more detailed calculation methodologies for estimating heat output from various wood sources in relation to fossil-fuel burning heating systems on a room by room basis is needed.

With thermal renovations, the complexity of the interrelationships of heat sources and building equipment is increasing. The proportion of heat provided by each system and at what time is very difficult to determine at this time, and further research is needed.

3.1 Economic Rebound Effects

An economic rebound effect is defined as the partial realization of potential energy savings caused by the homeowner's perception of cost savings. In actuality, there is higher consumption of energy services (Biermayr et al., 2005).

Because of the higher comfort level provided by less air infiltration and lower heat losses through the envelope, it is possible that the full energy and cost savings potentials are not reached in the case study homes.

3.2 Parametric study

Figures 11 and 12 compare the relative effects of different parameters on the heating energy demand for House 2. Figure 11 shows the relationship of the parameters under existing conditions, and Figure 12 illustrates the relationships of the variables with improved thermal renovations and updated building services.

Fig. 11. The effect of uncertainties on the heating energy demand using House 2 existing data

The impact of insulating the exterior envelope is clearly shown in this analysis. In the base case, it is the dominant factor and can increase the heating energy demand by up to 7%. In the renovated scenario, with additional the influence of the quality of the exterior envelope is reduced to less than 3%. The influence of indoor temperature is slightly greater in the renovated case; however, the relative influence of indoor temperature is less than the impact of natural ventilation and infiltration in the renovated house.

Fig. 12. The effect of uncertainties on the heating energy demand using House 2 renovated data

4. Development of new user models

The accuracy of the static user profile comes into question when comparing the estimated energy consumption values with actual use. As was seen, even when correcting the estimated values based on knowledge of user behaviour, the estimations do not match actual use which is supported by the findings in a report completed by (Hierzinger et al., 2011).

When compared to the three actual user profiles from the case study houses, discrepancies in user behaviour appear:

- Instead of 100% occupancy, by individual estimates, houses are occupied up to 75% of the time (16-18 h/day);
- Portions of the houses are either heated to different set point temperatures or not heated at all;
- Night temperature set-backs are not considered in the calculations;
- Estimated window ventilation rates vary between 0.01 and 0.26 h⁻¹ with an averaged value for single-sided ventilation for all three houses of 0.08 h⁻¹ and 0.10 h⁻¹ for cross-ventilation;
- The heat gains from electrical appliances vary according to the efficiencies of the individual appliances.

As part of the research work conducted by the Task Force for Occupant Behaviour of Annex 53, the relationship of occupant behaviour, building services and the quality of the exterior envelope of buildings is being studied.

5. Conclusions

The results showed that the calculated values exceeded actual energy consumption by up to 35%. The main reasons for the discrepancies between the estimated values in the Austrian energy certificate calculations and the actual consumption showed that detailed input data including information about user behaviour, building services, climate data, and building construction are needed for accurate estimations.

Corresponding to the findings in this study, research by Müller et al. (2010) and Knoter (2010) have also found that by improving the thermal envelope and building HVAC systems, a building's overall energy consumption can be decreased significantly. In the study by Müller et al. (2010), thermal renovations of existing homes are predicted to become increasingly important in Austria increasing the relevance of detailed studies such as this one to better understand the relationships of climate, building envelope and services, as well as occupant behaviour on overall energy use in buildings. Improving the user profile in the Austrian norms can increase the prediction accuracy of heating energy use for single family homes in energy certificate calculations, especially when natural ventilation habits are considered.

The combined effect of improving the thermal envelope, updating HVAC systems, and conscientious user behaviour can significantly decrease overall energy use in residential buildings. The accuracy of prediction tools can be increased by better consideration of user behaviour by using more sophisticated statistical models that consider the presence

probability of people. Additionally, more advanced infiltration and ventilation models should be used.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank the three families who participated in the study and generously opened the doors of their homes.

References

ASCHOFF, C. & GROTTJAN, H. 2004. *Frischluftechnik im Wohnungsbau*, Stuttgart, Gentner Verlag.

AUSTRIAN STANDARDS INSTITUTE 2010. Thermal insulation in building construction - part 5: model of climate and user profiles. *ÖNORM B 8110-5*. Vienna, Austria: Austrian Standards Institute.

BAUBOOK. 2011. *Ökologische Bauprodukte* [Online]. Vienna, Austria: baubook GmbH. Available: <http://www.baubook.at> [Accessed 25 May, 2011].

BIERMAYR, P., SCHREIFL, E., BAUMANN, B. & STURM, A. 2005. Maßnahmen zur Minimierung von Reboundeffekten bei der Sanierung von Wohngebäuden (MARESI). *Nachhaltig Wirtschaften*. Vienna, Austria: Bundesministerium für Verkehr, Innovation und Technologie.

COUNCIL OF THE EUROPEAN UNION 2002. Directive 2002/91/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2002 on the energy performance of buildings. *Official Journal of the European Communities*.

DÖRN, M. 2011. *Vergleich von Verbrauchsdaten mit Bedarfsberechnungen für den Energieeinsatz bei Einfamilienhäusern*. Master of Science Masters Thesis, Vienna University of Technology.

EUROPEAN COMMITTEE FOR STANDARDIZATION 2004. Thermal performance of buildings - Calculation of internal temperatures of a room in summer without mechanical cooling - General criteria and validation procedures. *prEN ISO 13791*. Brussels: CEN.

GUERRA SANTIN, O., ITARD, L. & VISSCHER, H. 2009. The effect of occupancy and building characteristics on energy use for space and water heating in Dutch residential stock. *Energy and Buildings*, 41, 1223-1232.

HIERZINGER, D. R., HERRY, D. M., SEISSER, O., STEINACHER, I. & WOLF-EBERL, M. S. March 2011. *RE: Energy Styles: Klimagerechtes Leben der Zukunft - Energy Styles als Ansatzpunkt für effiziente Policy Interventions*. Type to ENERGIEFONDS, K.-U.

KNOTER, A. 2010. SQUARE: Qualitätssicherungsmaßnahmen zur Verbesserung des Wohnraumklimas und der Energieeffizienz bei der Sanierung von großvolumigen Wohngebäuden. *Nachhaltig Wirtschaften*. Gleisdorf.

KYRÖ, R., HEINONEN, J., SÄYNÄJOKI, A. & JUNNILA, S. 2011. Occupants have little influence on the overall energy consumption in district heated apartment buildings. *Energy and Buildings*, 43, 3484-3490.

MÜLLER, A., BIERMAYR, P., KRANZL, L., HAAS, R., ALTENBURGER, F., BERGMANN, I., FRIEDL, G.,

Proceedings of the 5th IBPC, Kyoto, Japan, May 28-31, 2012
HASLINGER, W., HEIMRATH, R., OHNMACHT, R. & WEISS, W. 2010. Heizen 2050: Systeme zur Wärmebereitstellung und Raumklimatisierung im österreichischen Gebäudebestand: Technologische Anforderungen bis zum Jahr 2050. Vienna, Austria.

ÖSTERREICHISCHES INSTITUT FÜR BAUTECHNIK 2007. Leitfaden Energietechnisches Verhalten von Gebäuden. Vienna, Austria: Österreichisches Institut für Bautechnik.

ÖSTERREICHISCHES INSTITUT FÜR BAUTECHNIK 2011. Erläuternde Bemerkungen zu OIB-Richtlinie 6 "Energieeinsparung und Wärmeschutz" und zum OIB-Leitfaden Energietechnisches Verhalten von Gebäuden". *OIB-330.6-092/11*. Vienna, Austria: Österreichisches Institut für Bautechnik.